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**Series 3: Decoding the Astronomical Characteristics Depicted on the Narmer Palette, the
Narmer Macehead and the Scorpion Macehead**

Chen, Lin

Translated by Xunzhe

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Abstract

The ancient Egyptian cultural artifacts of the Narmer Palette, the Narmer Macehead and the Scorpion Macehead separately depict the characteristic astronomical and calendar phenomena that occurred on certain major historical events. Therefore, the exact times and astronomical and calendar characteristics corresponding to the narratives on the three artifacts can be retrieved with the tool of astronomical software. The demonstration in this article is an important supplement to the chronological study on ancient Egypt, and also constitutes strong evidence for the study on the relationship between ancient Egyptian civilization and ancient Huaxia civilization.

Key Words

The Narmer Palette, the Narmer Macehead, the Scorpion Macehead, astronomical characteristics, Egyptian hieroglyphs, ancient Egyptian civilization, Huaxia Civilization

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After carefully studying the Dendera Zodiac, the author has learnt that ancient Egyptians used human and animal figures to symbolize astronomical phenomena. Later, the author did a study on Egyptian hieroglyphs and had amazing findings. The author will discuss the findings in detail in another article, and here an example of the findings is given to discuss the decoding process of the three artifacts. As shown in Figure 1, the title of "Shu" is composed of three hieroglyphic characters, and the three characters are polyphonic and polysemy respectively as follows:

Left: Shi (室), Chi (池), Xiang (象)

Middle: Yu (羽), Lu (律), Shu / Xiao (蜀、鸮), Xun / Fen (巽、分)

Right: Wu (乌), Niao (鸟), Lü (律), Liu (柳), Wan / Wang (鸛、王), Yong (俑)

Figure 1

If pronouncing the three characters in the way of "Fanqie" (反切) or "Qieyun" (切韵) (traditional spelling method of Chinese characters), that is, the initial consonant of the previous

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character is spelled to the vowel of the next character from left to right, various titles can be spelled out, such as “Shu Wang” (蜀王, an ancient King recorded in Chinese documents), “Xuan Lü” (玄律, the name of the Yellow Emperor), “Xuan Niao” (玄鸟, the rotating bird), and “Chi You” (蚩尤, the rebellious Yan Emperor killed by the Yellow Emperor), “Qu Yuan” (屈原, a legendary figure in Chinese history).

Since these are also the titles of the great figures in Huaxia civilization, it reminds the author of the Narmer Palette that depicts a scene of King Narmer killing a man (Figure 2). The author realizes that this must be the depiction of the astronomical phenomenon on the day that “the Yellow Emperor (Narmer) killed “Chi You”. It is a well-known story in China.

Notes:

The author believes that Egyptian hieroglyphs were originally ancient Chinese characters, and they pronounced ancient Chinese sounds. These pronunciations are still preserved in the dialects from southwest China to the southeast coast, especially in Hokkien, Wu and Hakka.

Figure 2

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The same as the Dendera Zodiac, the conical symbol on Figure 3 is the "丙丁 (Bing Ding)" symbol representing the summer solstice. The summer solstice point is between "the big guy" (the Yellow Emperor, representing Leo) and "the young man to his right" (Sirius), which represents the summer solstice point between the seventeen stars of Xuanyuan (Leo) and Sirius. At the same time, to the right of Sirius, "the four little guys holding the flags" symbolizes "four stars in a line".

According to Chinese historical documents, the day that "the Emperor Yellow" killed the rebellious "Chi You" must be the fifth day of the fifth lunar month and happen to be the summer solstice as well.

Figure 3

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To verify whether the author's judgment is correct, it has to confirm whether the fifth day of the fifth lunar month in a certain year happened to be the summer solstice, and at the same time, the astronomical phenomena depicted on the Narmer Palette appeared.

The author used the software Stellarium and set the observation site at "Zhuolu" (涿鹿) (Sohag by the Nile River) to search for this particular day. A wonderful situation appeared—On July 16, 2,684 BC (astronomical year-2683), the fifth day of the fifth month of the lunar calendar, also the day of the summer solstice, as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, and Saturn are in a line to the west of the sun, and Mars is to the east of the sun.

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Figure 4

Figure 5

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Figure 6, 7, the famous "Narmer Macehead " is also the depiction of astronomical characteristics. Mars is "the guy on the left bottom carrying the shoes and a jug". Sirius is "the guy on the top of Mars" and their ecliptic longitudes are very close. "The three bearded men on the boat" represents "the three stars of Orion". The scene of "King Narmer's marriage" symbolizes "the Sun and the Moon getting together". The sun is between the three stars of Orion and Sirius. "The four little guys holding flags" symbolize "four stars in a line". Searched by the software, the day with these features can be only found May 3, 3,128 BC, the first day of the third lunar month (Figure 8, 9).

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Similarly, the Scorpion Macehead is also the depiction of astronomical characteristics. As shown in Figure 10, “the highlighted scorpion” is Scorpio, the “flower” on the top of the “scorpion” is Mars. The combination of Mars and scorpion is not the sign of "Scorpion King", but symbolizes on the day that “Yellow Emperor was personally farming”, Mars was located on the top of Scorpio. To the right of Mars, there are “four stars in a row”. In front of the Yellow Emperor, there is “a guy holding a broom-shaped object”, which is "Shi" (师), representing Shi Hexagram of the 64 Hexagram, corresponding to the autumnal equinox.

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Searched by the software, the day with these features can be only found October 22, 2,966 BC (astronomical year-2965) (Figure 11). On this day, Mars entered the Room Mansion sky zone from the west; on October 28, Mars moved eastward and left the Room Mansion sky zone.

During these seven days, the four planets Mercury, Saturn, Jupiter and Venus to the west of Mars lined up in turn. (Figure 11, 12)

Figure 10

Fig 53. Relief on mace head of King Scorpion, late Predynastic (ca. 3100 B.C.E.). Ashmolean Museum, Oxford. Drawing by Richard Parkinson after Marion Cox after Spencer 1993

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Figure 11

Figure 12

